

MONTESSORI EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOLERS.

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Abstract. *In the classrooms of teachers, there ought to be a balance of direct instruction, guided play, and student-directed play. Children can use their creativity, language, social skills, self-control, and other talents to the fullest extent while playing. The best learning occurs when students are given a wide variety of options for activities and topics that engage them. Montessori education places a special emphasis on assisting children in developing their sensory abilities. An organized, aesthetically beautiful, and well-organized Montessori environment gives kids a sense of security and promotes discovery. Children's freedom to roam, select, and participate in self-directed activities helps them uncover their passions and potential. The ability to lose yourself in an activity is encouraged in Montessori programs. Having a choice and feeling in control of one's environment is associated with better performance. Kids who have a consistent family schedule and are considered to be more organized perform better in terms of cognitive, psychological, and social development. To encourage further study and to better inform teachers about whether as well as why the Montessori Method might be helpful, the paper's objective is to present an overview of the evidence foundation for the method.*

Keywords: *Montessori Method, activities, children, play, research, learning, tools, competence.*

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ МОНТЕССОРИ В ДОШКОЛЬНИКАХ.

Аннотация. *В классах учителей должен быть баланс между непосредственным обучением, управляемой игрой и игрой, управляемой учеником. Дети могут в полной мере использовать свои творческие способности, язык, социальные навыки, самоконтроль и другие таланты во время игры. Лучшее обучение происходит, когда учащимся предоставляется широкий выбор вариантов деятельности и тем, которые их интересуют. Монтессори-педагогика уделяет особое внимание развитию сенсорных способностей детей. Организованная, эстетически красивая и хорошо организованная Монтессори-среда дает детям чувство безопасности и способствует открытию. Свобода детей бродить, выбирать и участвовать в самостоятельных мероприятиях помогает им раскрыть свои увлечения и потенциал. В программах Монтессори поощряется способность полностью погрузиться в деятельность. Наличие выбора и чувство контроля над окружающей средой связано с лучшей производительностью. Дети, которые имеют постоянный семейный график и считаются более организованными, лучше развиваются с точки зрения когнитивного, психологического и социального развития. Чтобы стимулировать дальнейшее изучение и лучше информировать учителей о том, может ли метод Монтессори быть полезным, а также почему, цель статьи состоит в том, чтобы представить обзор доказательной базы для метода.*

Ключевые слова: метод Монтессори, деятельность, дети, игра, исследование, обучение, инструменты, компетентность.

INTRODUCTION

It may appear at first glance that early education serves only to acclimate children to school life and provide them with an opportunity for socialization. But your child's life will be impacted by the early childhood program you choose for them. The very first six years of a kid's development are among the most crucial for growth and can have a long-lasting effect on a child's process of growing up, according to several educational experts. Teachers have a crucial role in fostering children's growth and development, especially in early childhood education. As a consequence, it is the teacher's responsibility to organize a sequence of educational activities in a preschool environment that starts with the creation of educational activities and continues through execution and evaluation. The ability of instructors to fulfill their professional obligations and complete tasks based on educational objectives determines whether the teaching and learning process in early education is successful or unsuccessful. Due to these obligations, teachers must stick to the lesson outline and make sure that instruction is given on time to support students' growth. The idea of "play" must be considered when monitoring children.

Important ideas for planning and teaching lessons

Early childhood educators provide children with many opportunities to play because they are aware that play is essential for children to feel joy and wonder. In the classrooms of teachers, there ought to be a balance of direct instruction, guided play, and student-directed play. Children can use their creativity, language, social skills, self-control, and other talents to the fullest extent while playing, allowing them to apply what they have learned. Additionally, it offers teachers a rare chance to watch youngsters at play and study their abilities and understandings. It should be equally possible for every child to decide whatever they acquire, whether they learn it or who they gain it from. By offering resources and tools that are founded on scrutiny of children's choice of play activity, educators promote and extend children's play experiences. Through activities that are directed by an adult and offer the students a sense of agency, teachers scaffold and extend the focus, engagement, and knowledge of the students.

Children are actively and stably engaged in demanding to learn when instructors plan relevant first-hand experiences for them. The best learning occurs when students are given a wide variety of options for activities, topics that engage them, and teachers who demonstrate their particular areas of competence in the classroom. Children have the chance to periodically reflect on and reengage with their educational experiences when materials are rotated and revisited. By offering resources and tools that are founded on scrutiny of children's choice of play activity, educators promote and extend children's play experiences. Through activities that are directed by an adult and offer the students a sense of agency, teachers scaffold and extend the focus, engagement, and knowledge of the students. Children are actively and stably engaged in demanding to learn when instructors plan relevant first-hand experiences for them. The best learning occurs when students are given a wide variety of options for activities, topics that engage them, and teachers who demonstrate their particular areas of competence in the classroom. Children have the chance to periodically reflect on and reengage with their educational experiences when materials are rotated and revisited.

The Montessori Method aims to support children in realizing their full potential by allowing them the opportunity to explore a setting that is created to match their unique developmental and educational needs and that empowers them to take charge of their education. Children receive assistance in growing their sense of self-worth, self-awareness, and consciousness to become civically engaged and socially responsible adults. However, because the Montessori Method is unregulated and neither patented nor trademarked, any practices that deviate from the basic methodology may be referred to as Montessori.

THE MONTESSORI METHOD `S CHARACTERISTICS

The Montessori Method relies heavily on the learning environment, which is purposefully created to encourage children's independent learning and positive decision-making. An organized, aesthetically beautiful, predictable, and well-organized Montessori environment gives kids a sense of security and promotes discovery. Each activity has its own space, and activities can be set up on trays with all the necessary materials arranged logically, such as from left to right in the sequence of use. Order is supposed to encourage children's autonomy and self-directed learning, as well as assist them in organizing their observations as they attempt to comprehend the outside world.

Children have the right to choose, but their options are constrained by the available materials and by the expectations that they act responsibly and constructively, in keeping with a focus on social behavior and self-discipline in particular. Children must, for instance, put finished activities back on the shelves so that other children can use them. Activities that emphasize organizing, placing objects in their appropriate places, or keeping things tidy are frequently employed, and it is believed that this supports children's perceptions of competence while also teaching them to concentrate their efforts and follow instructions. Montessori attempted to encourage abstract cognition using the environment, movement, and aesthetics because she understood the important connection between the body, emotions, and intellect. The majority of activities in the Montessori Method include moving the whole body or manipulating items with the hands. Movement is viewed as essential to cognitive development.

Montessori education places a special emphasis on assisting children in developing their sensory abilities (including visual, auditory, tactile, and chromatic or color feeling), making a distinction between increasingly complicated properties, and categorizing these by sorting, matching, pairing, and creating patterns. These sensory encounters are believed to serve as the foundation for the conceptual growth necessary for later academic learning. Since the Montessori Method emphasizes each child's uniqueness, observation is a crucial pedagogical technique for comprehending children's learning and designing appropriate activities. Children's freedom to roam, select, and participate in self-directed activities helps them uncover their passions and potential while educating adults on how to best assist their learning.

RESULTS

There aren't many empirical research studies that specifically assess how the Montessori Method affects kids' learning. Additionally, because the Montessori Method can be applied in a variety of ways, generalizations are challenging. Yet, researchers in one study assessed groups of children aged five to 12 who attended Montessori and conventional schools and found no differences in their demographics, including family income or parents' educational levels. It was shown that students attending Montessori schools achieved outcomes that were on par with or

better than those at regular schools, including improved reading, math, executive function, and social competence. Children who attended a Montessori preschool also outperformed a control group in terms of educational attainment, contextual awareness, commitment to learning, executive function, and good school attitudes.

According to the research, having a choice and feeling in control of one's environment and activities is associated with better performance, increased engagement, concentration, and persistence in work, improved well-being, a positive self-concept, and enhanced learning, memory, and problem-solving skills. The ability to lose yourself in an activity—which is encouraged in Montessori programs—shares similarities with the process theory of ultimate convenience, and a large body of research links flow to beneficial outcomes for kids. The linkage between schoolchildren's physical skills and their social knowledge is shown in research on the interaction between motion and cognition, which shows the relationship between activity and improved brain functioning. Other research demonstrates that movement enhances children's conceptions of distance and objects and that hand movements promote spatial dilemmas and spatial reasoning.

Research on sensitive period six reveals that kids are interested in signals that are simultaneously novel and at the proper level of complexity for deepening their knowledge. For instance, babies are drawn to patterns that have precisely the right complexity to support their highly accurate development. According to research in favor of order, routines, and organizations, kids who have consistent family schedules and whose homes are considered to be more organized perform better in terms of cognitive, psychological, and social development. Studies have also shown that conceptually organized information, such as material categorized by concept or according to relationships between ideas, is easier to acquire and recall than information that is randomly organized. Early sensory experiences lay a crucial foundation for many higher-level skills, according to research on the significance of early subjective perception, which also demonstrates how increased sensory input favorably impacts the brain's organization and architecture.

CONCLUSION

An examination of the Montessori philosophy may provide educators with a chance to consider how to better implement pedagogical strategies like observation or how to provide children with structured learning experiences through the choice and presentation of resources. The evidence for Montessori education that adheres to the creator's ideals has been covered in this essay, but it is less obvious whether adapted forms—which generally result in kids spending fewer hours engaged with self-selected learning materials—are as successful. However, studies show that practical learning materials can be helpfully incorporated into non-Montessori classrooms to encourage the growth of young children's fine motor capabilities and attention, and there is plenty of proof from the diverse educational literary works that certain components of the Montessori method—like having to teach children's learning throughout a phonemic awareness approach engrained in a rich language context and supplying a multisensory basis for mathematics education—are effective.

Focus on developing and maintaining ordered surroundings that provide kids with the tools and resources they need to follow their interests if you want to start incorporating the benefits of the Montessori Method into your teaching. Consider how you can make the environment predictable while still being able to offer interesting new things. Reduce clutter, make spaces more

aesthetically pleasing, and employ environmental design to show kids how to participate in various activities.

Offering self-contained activities on shelves could improve settings. Children should be shown how to utilize these tools and how they can reassemble them in the proper order after using them. Use a tray, for instance, on which each item's outline has been sketched. Think about how you might gather and arrange these loose parts to emphasize specific qualities, such as providing different grades of abrasive paper to compare or simply putting items with different odors in ambiguous bins so that they can only be researched by smell. Also, consider offering pieces to support children's sensory investigations.

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